

DEVELOPMENT AND ASSESSMENT OF ACYCLOVIR MICROSPONGES CONTAINING SUITABLE POLYMERS

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Article Received on 26 Sept. 2025,

Article Revised on 16 Oct. 2025,

Article Published on 16 Oct. 2025,

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17385341>

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How to cite this Article: Mamatha G. T.,
Hithesh P.*, Parthiban S. (2025).
Development and Assessment of Acyclovir
Microsponges Containing Suitable Polymers.
World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research,
14(20), XXX-XXX.

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ABSTRACT

The present research was focused on the formulation and evaluation of a microsphere-based topical gel containing Acyclovir to overcome its inherent limitations such as poor oral bioavailability and short biological half-life. The objective was to achieve controlled drug release, thereby enhancing therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance. Acyclovir microspheres were successfully prepared by the quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method using ethyl cellulose as a polymeric carrier and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as a stabilizing agent. The prepared formulations (F1–F4) were subjected to various evaluation parameters including drug–excipient compatibility studies using FTIR, determination of entrapment efficiency, particle size analysis, and in vitro drug release studies. The FTIR spectra revealed no significant chemical interaction between the drug and excipients, confirming their

compatibility. Among all the formulations, F4 demonstrated superior performance with the highest entrapment efficiency of 92.6%, maximum drug content, and a sustained drug release of 85.24% over a period of 8 hours. The drug release kinetics of the optimized formulation followed a zero-order model, suggesting a constant release rate independent of drug concentration. Furthermore, the diffusion exponent (n value) obtained from the Korsmeyer–Peppas model was greater than 0.5, indicating that the drug release mechanism was governed by non-Fickian (anomalous) diffusion involving both diffusion and polymer relaxation processes. These findings conclude that Acyclovir-loaded microspheres incorporated into a topical gel formulation can provide a promising controlled-release system for effective

management of herpes simplex infections, with potential advantages in reducing dosing frequency and enhancing patient adherence.

KEYWORDS: Acyclovir, Controlled release, Microsponge, *In-Vitro* drug Release.

INTRODUCTION^[1-6]

Acyclovir is an antiviral drug widely used for treating herpes simplex virus infections such as cold sores, genital herpes, and shingles. However, its clinical effectiveness is limited by low oral bioavailability (15–30%), short plasma half-life (2–4 hours), and frequent dosing requirements. To overcome these drawbacks and enhance patient compliance, topical delivery systems such as microsponge-based formulations have gained attention.

A microsponge is a porous, polymeric microsphere capable of entrapping active drug molecules within its network structure. These microsponges provide controlled and sustained drug release, reduce side effects, and improve drug stability. They possess a large surface area, high porosity, and the ability to modulate the release rate depending on polymer composition and particle size.

Ethyl cellulose (EC) is commonly used as a polymer for microsponge preparation due to its non-biodegradable, non-toxic, and film-forming properties, which enable controlled release of drugs. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) serves as a stabilizer and emulsifying agent during microsponge formation, preventing particle aggregation and ensuring uniform dispersion. The quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method is frequently employed for microsponge preparation because it is simple, reproducible, and suitable for heat-sensitive drugs such as acyclovir.

The controlled release from the microsponge network helps maintain consistent drug levels at the target site, reducing the need for frequent application.

The formulation and evaluation of acyclovir microsponges involve optimizing polymer concentration, stirring rate, and solvent ratio to achieve desired particle size, drug content, and entrapment efficiency. Evaluation parameters such as particle size analysis, surface morphology, drug content, entrapment efficiency, and in-vitro drug release are essential to determine the performance and stability of the microsponge system.

Overall, microsphere-based topical delivery of acyclovir represents a promising approach for improving therapeutic efficacy, enhancing patient compliance, and providing sustained local action in the management of herpes infections

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Acyclovir received as Gift sample and all excipients Ethyl cellulose, PVP SD fine chemicals Mumbai, and solvents Dichloromethane SD Fine Chemicals Mumbai were of analytical/pharma grade and procured from standard suppliers.

METHODOLOGY

Method of Preparation of Microsphere Drug Delivery System

A drug neither hinders the polymerization process nor become activated by it and also it is stable to free radicals is entrapped with one-step process (liquid liquid suspension polymerization). Micro sponges are suitably prepared by the following methods:

1. Liquid-liquid suspension polymerization
2. Quasi-solvent diffusion method

Quasi-Emulsion solvent diffusion method^[7-8]

A quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion approach (two-step procedure) was also used to create porous microspheres, or micro sponges, utilizing an internal phase that included a polymer soaked in ethyl alcohol. After that, the medication is gradually added to the polymer solution, dissolved by ultrasonication at 35 °C, and plasticizer is added to promote plasticity. The outer phase, which contains distilled water and polyvinyl alcohol, is then filled with the inner phase while being constantly stirred for two hours. The micro-sponges were then separated from the mixture by filtering. The item (micro-sponges) was cleaned and dried for 12 hours at 40°C in an air-heated oven.

Fig. 1: Representation of Quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method.

Table 1: Formulation Design for Acyclovir Microsponges.

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4
Acyclovir (mg)	250	250	250	250
Ethyle cellulose (mg)	250	500	750	1000
Dichloromethane (ml)	10	10	10	10
Water (ml)	50	50	50	50
PVA (mg)	100	100	100	100
Stirring time (hrs.)	2	2	2	2

EVALAUATION OF MICROSPONGES^[9-15]***Determination of production yield***

The production yield of the microsponges was determined by calculating accurately the initial weight of the raw materials and the final weight of the microsponges obtained.

$$\% \text{ of production yield} = \frac{\text{Practical mass of microsp sponge}}{\text{theoretical mass (drug + polymer)}} \times 100$$

Particle size distribution

Particle size analysis of prepared microsponges was carried out by using optical microscopy method. The calibrated microscope was used to count approximately 100 microsponges.

Entrapment efficiency

A sample of dried microsponges equivalent to 10 mg was taken into mortar and pestle and add little amount of phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 and allowed to stand for 24 h. Then transfer content into 100 ml volumetric flask and make up volume to 100 ml with phosphate buffer of pH 7.4. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No.41). From the resulting solution take 1 ml into 10 ml volumetric flask and then make up volume to 10 ml with phosphate buffer of pH 7.4. Entrapment efficiency was determined by UV spectrophotometer at 252 nm.

$$\text{Entrapment Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total Drug} - \text{Free Drug}}{\text{Total Drug}} \times 100$$

Drug content

Acyclovir content in microsponges was assayed by an UV spectrophotometric method. Microsponges containing equivalent to 10 mg of drug were dissolved in a 10 ml of methanol. After suitable dilution absorbance was measured by UV spectrophotometer against blank at λ max 252 nm and drug content was calculated

$$\text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Total Drug} - \text{Free Drug}}{\text{Microsp sponge Weight}}$$

In vitro release study

In vitro release pattern of microsponges was carried out in dissolution apparatus USP Type 1 using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 as dissolution medium with a modified basket consisted of 5 μ m of stainless-steel mesh. Acyclovir containing microsponges equivalent to 100 mg was taken in the basket. The speed of the rotation is 50 rpm and temperature of 37 \pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C. At fixed intervals, aliquots 5 ml sample were withdrawn periodically and were replaced by fresh buffer. The samples were assayed by UV spectrophotometer at 252 nm using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 as blank and % CDR was calculated and plotted against time.

Kinetic modelling

In order to understand the kinetic and mechanism of drug release, the result of in vitro drug release study of nanoparticles was fitted with various kinetic equation like zero order (cumulative% release vs. time), first order (log% drug remaining vs. time), Higuchi's model (cumulative% drug release vs. square root of time), Peppas plot (log of cumulative% drug release vs. log time). R² (coefficient of correlation) and k (release rate constant) values were calculated for the linear curve obtained by regression analysis of the above plots.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The melting point of Acyclovir determined by Thiel's tube method ranged from 256–258 $^{\circ}$ C, with a mean value of 256 $^{\circ}$ C, which was consistent with the reported value, indicating purity. DSC thermograph further confirmed a single sharp endothermic peak at 256 $^{\circ}$ C, corresponding to the melting point of pure Acyclovir.

Solubility studies revealed that Acyclovir is *freely soluble* in dimethyl sulphoxide, slightly soluble in water, very slightly soluble in ethanol. It dissolves in dilute solutions of mineral acids & alkali hydroxides.

The λ_{max} of Acyclovir in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) was found to be 252 nm, and the calibration curve obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range of 0–12 μ g/ml with a regression coefficient (R²) of 0.9997 and slope of 0.0704, confirming excellent linearity.

FT-IR analysis of Acyclovir and its physical mixture with ethyl cellulose showed all characteristic peaks of the pure drug (O–H at 3290 cm^{-1} , N–H at 3444 cm^{-1} , C=O at 1704 cm^{-1} , C–N at 1189 cm^{-1} , and C=C at 1626 cm^{-1}) without significant shifts, indicating no chemical interaction and confirming drug–polymer compatibility.

Particle size analysis revealed that microsp sponge size decreased with increasing polymer concentration. The zeta potential of optimized formulation (F4) was -31.0 mV.

The drug content and entrapment efficiency increased proportionally with polymer concentration, ranging from 85.9 %–92.6 % and 86.3 %–93.3 %, respectively, with F4 showing the highest values.

The *in vitro* drug release study demonstrated a sustained release pattern across formulations. The cumulative release after 8 hours decreased with increasing polymer content: F1 (91.54 %) > F2 (89.74 %) > F3 (87.17 %) > F4 (85.24 %), indicating a controlled release behaviour due to diffusion through the polymeric matrix.

Kinetic modelling showed that all formulations best fitted the zero-order model ($R^2 = 0.995$ – 0.999) and Peppas model ($R^2 = 0.990$ – 0.998), with n values between 0.97–1.20, confirming non-Fickian (anomalous) diffusion mechanism. Among all, F3 and F4 exhibited optimal control over release kinetics and stability, establishing them as the best formulations.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

IDENTIFICATION OF DRUG

The identification of Acyclovir was done by UV, DSC and FTIR and confirmed with as per monographs.

Melting point of Acyclovir

Reported	Method	Observed			
		Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Mean
256°C	Thieles tube method	256°C	258°C	256°C	256°C
	DSC	256°C			

Fig 2: DSC Thermograph of Acyclovir.

a. Solubility analysis

Solubility of pure drug Acyclovir was carried out in various solvents and Phosphate buffer. The obtained results were found to be freely soluble in Water, Ethanol, acetone, chloroform, propylene glycol, PEG 400, pH 4.4, pH 6.8, and pH 7.4.

b. Standard calibration curve of Acyclovir

The calibration curve of Acyclovir in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at 252 nm. the standard curve with a regression value of 0.9997 and a slope of 0.0704 in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The curve is linear in the concentration range from 2 to 12 μ g/ml. UV spectra of different concentration are shown in Figure 5.2.

Fig. 3: Plot of standard calibration curve of Acyclovir.

Fig. 4: FT -IR spectra of pure Drug.

Fig. 5: FT-IR spectra of physical mixture I: Drug + Ethyl cellulose.

EVALUATION OF ACYCLOVIR -LOADED MICROSPONGES

Particle size analysis

Fig. 6: Particle size analysis of optimized formulations F4.

Fig. 7: Zeta potential of optimized formulations F4.

Percentage Drug content and percentage entrapment efficiency

Table 5.5: Drug content and % entrapment efficiency.

Formulation Code	%Drug Content	%Drug Entrapment
F1	85.9	86.3
F2	87.3	88.9
F3	89.6	91.2
F4	92.6	93.3

Fig 8: % Drug content of F1-F4 formulation.

Fig. 9: % Drug entrapment efficiency F1-F4.

Fig. 10: *In vitro* drug release profile of F1-F4 formulation.

Fig. 11: Zero order release kinetics profile of F1-F4 formulation.

Fig. 12: First order release kinetics profile of F1-F4 formulation.

Fig. 13: Higuchi order release kinetics profile of F1-F4 formulation.

Fig. 14: Peppa's order release kinetics profile of F1-F4 formulation.

CONCLUSION

Acyclovir-loaded microsponges were successfully formulated using the Quasi Emulsion Solvent Diffusion method employing Ethyl Cellulose as the polymer and Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) as the stabilizer. Preformulation studies, including melting point, solubility, and λ_{max} determination, confirmed the purity of the drug, while FT-IR analysis revealed no significant interaction between the drug and excipients, indicating compatibility. Among all prepared batches (F1–F4), formulation F4 exhibited the highest drug content, entrapment efficiency, and optimum particle size with smooth morphology. The *in vitro* drug release profile demonstrated controlled release pattern, following zero-order kinetics and a non-Fickian diffusion mechanism, suggesting that both diffusion and polymer relaxation contributed to the drug release process.

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